

Influence of Culture Media on Growth and Sclerotia formation of *Rhizoctonia solani*

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ABSTRACT

Rhizoctonia solani is an important soil-borne fungal pathogen responsible for significant yield losses in many crops. The present study was conducted to evaluate the effect of different culture media on the growth and cultural characteristics of *Rhizoctonia solani* under in vitro conditions. Six different media, namely Corn Meal Agar, Czapek Dox Agar, Glucose Nitrate Agar, Malt Extract Agar, Nutrient Agar and Potato Dextrose Agar were used for the study. The results revealed significant variation in colony diameter, texture, pigmentation and sclerotia formation across different media. Maximum radial growth was observed on Czapek Dox Agar while minimum growth was recorded on Glucose Nitrate Agar. Early initiation and higher formation of sclerotia were observed in Malt Extract Agar and Czapek Dox Agar, whereas no sclerotia formation was recorded in Glucose Nitrate Agar and Nutrient Agar. The study concludes that culture media significantly influence the growth and morphological characteristics of *Rhizoctonia solani*.

Keywords: *Rhizoctonia solani*, Culture media, Colony characteristics, Sclerotia

INTRODUCTION

Rhizoctonia solani is a widely distributed soil-borne fungal pathogen that infects a broad range of host plants, causing diseases such as damping-off, root rot, and stem canker, leading to substantial agricultural losses worldwide (Dean *et al.*, 2012). The pathogen survives in soil primarily through resistant structures such as sclerotia, which enable it to persist under adverse environmental conditions and initiate infection when favorable conditions arise. Due to its destructive nature and wide host range, *R. solani* has been recognized as one of the most economically important plant pathogenic fungi (Anderson, 1982; Dean *et al.*, 2012).

In vitro cultural studies are essential for understanding fungal biology, identification, and variability, as well as for developing effective disease management strategies (Barnett & Hunter, 2006). Variations in media composition can lead to differences in enzyme production and sclerotial development, which are directly linked to pathogenicity.

Sclerotia formation is a crucial survival and reproductive mechanism in *Rhizoctonia solani*, playing a vital role in its life cycle and disease spread. The initiation and development of sclerotia are highly dependent on nutritional and environmental conditions, particularly the type of culture medium used (Chet & Henis, 1975; Willetts & Bullock, 1992). Previous studies have demonstrated that media rich in nutrients favor both mycelial growth and sclerotia production, while nutrient-deficient media may restrict these processes (Papavizas & Davey, 1961; Punja, 1985). Therefore, evaluating the influence of different culture media on the growth and sclerotia formation of *R. solani* is essential for better understanding its biology and improving laboratory culture techniques.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Culture and Media Preparation

A pure culture of *Rhizoctonia solani* was used for the study. Six different culture media, namely Corn Meal Agar, Czapek Dox Agar, Glucose Nitrate Agar, Malt Extract Agar, Nutrient Agar, and Potato Dextrose Agar, were prepared, sterilized, and poured into Petri plates under aseptic conditions.

2. Inoculation and Incubation

The sterilized media plates were inoculated with a 5 mm disc of actively growing fungal culture. The inoculated plates were then incubated at 27±1°C under controlled laboratory conditions for proper growth.

3. Observations

Growth parameters such as colony diameter along with cultural characteristics including texture, pigmentation, and sclerotia formation were evaluated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The observations presented in Table 1 and Plate 1 show significant variation in colony growth and cultural characteristics of *Rhizoctonia solani* on different culture media. The cultural characteristics of *Rhizoctonia solani* were evaluated on six different culture media, which revealed significant variation in its growth and morphology. Maximum radial growth was observed on Czapek Dox Agar (88.50 mm), followed by Malt Extract Agar (79.33 mm) and Potato Dextrose Agar (73.44 mm), whereas minimum growth was recorded on Glucose Nitrate Agar (20.51 mm) and Nutrient Agar (38.16 mm).

Table 1: Colony Characteristics of *Rhizoctonia solani*

Sr. No.	Media	Colony Diameter in mm (3 rd day)	Colony Characters	
			Texture	Pigmentation
1	Corn Meal Agar	66.66 ± 1.01	Velvety thin	Light grey mycelium, greyish pigmentation without concentric rings
2	Czapek Dox Agar	88.5 ± 1.32	Velvety thick	Grey mycelium, grey pigmentation with two concentric rings
3	Glucose Nitrate Agar	20.51 ± 0.48	Sparse thin	White mycelium without pigmentation
4	Malt extract agar	79.33 ± 0.90	Velvety thick	Grey mycelium, light grey pigmentation with two concentric rings
5	Nutrient Agar	38.16 ± 1.04	Sparse thin	White mycelium without pigmentation
6	Potato Dextrose Agar	73.44 ± 0.81	Velvety thick	Light grey mycelium, blackish pigmentation with two concentric rings

Table 2: Sclerotial Characteristics of *Rhizoctonia solani*

Sr. No.	Media	Sclerotia		
		Initiation	Distribution	Formation
1	Corn Meal Agar	10 th day	Centre	++
2	Czapek Dox Agar	7 th day	Periphery	+++
3	Glucose Nitrate Agar	None	None	None
4	Malt extract agar	5 th day	All over	++++
5	Nutrient Agar	None	None	None
6	Potato Dextrose Agar	7 th day	All over	+++

++ = Least, +++ = Moderate, ++++ = Heavy

Plate 1: Cultural & sclerotial Characteristics of *Rhizoctonia solani* on Various Media

The colony exhibited a velvety texture with grey-colored mycelium. Pigmentation ranging from grey to black was evident on most media; however, no pigmentation was observed on Glucose Nitrate Agar and Nutrient Agar.

The results related to sclerotia formation are presented in Table 2 and Plate 1, which indicate that culture media significantly influenced sclerotial development in *R. solani*. Malt Extract Agar was found to be the most favorable medium for sclerotial production. No sclerotia were formed on Glucose Nitrate Agar and Nutrient Agar, while Czapek Dox Agar, Potato Dextrose Agar, and Corn Meal Agar supported sclerotial formation. Furthermore, the distribution pattern of sclerotia varied among the different media, indicating that nutrient composition plays a crucial role in sclerotial development.

The results indicate that the growth and sclerotial development of *Rhizoctonia solani* are greatly influenced by the composition of culture media. Maximum growth on Czapek Dox Agar and Malt Extract Agar may be due to the availability of suitable nutrients that enhance fungal growth (Paulitz & Schroeder, 2005; Xue et al., 2008). In contrast, reduced growth and lack of pigmentation on Glucose Nitrate Agar and Nutrient Agar suggest nutrient limitations. Higher sclerotial formation on nutrient-rich media further confirms that environmental and nutritional factors play a key role in the development of survival structures in *R. solani* (González et al., 2006; Ajayi-Oyetunde & Bradley, 2018; Mishra & Kanaujia, 2012).

Similar variability in cultural behavior of *R. solani* under different nutritional conditions has been reported by earlier workers, emphasizing that environmental factors significantly influence its growth pattern and survival mechanisms (Sharma et al., 2013; Meena et al., 2014; Dubey et al., 2016).

CONCLUSION

The present study concludes that the growth and cultural characteristics of *Rhizoctonia solani* vary significantly depending on the composition of culture media. Nutrient-rich media such as Czapek Dox Agar, Malt Extract Agar, and Potato Dextrose Agar promote better mycelial growth and sclerotia formation. In contrast, nutrient-deficient media restrict fungal development, highlighting the importance of media selection for in vitro studies of the pathogen.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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